

Juvenile hormone analogues active on mosquitoes : Synthesis and juvenile hormonal activity of newly synthesized juvenoid ethers with α -pinene and substituted cyclohexane ring in the terminal position

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1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene (1), 1-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene (2) and their analogues have been synthesised and the compounds tested on *Culex pipiens quinquefasciatus* Say. for their juvenile hormone activity.

Literature records¹ that compounds structurally related to natural insect juvenile hormones with an ether linkage in the molecule exhibit biological activity. The discovery of juvabione and dehydrojuvabione as potent juvenile hormones by Bowers² and Cerney³ from the Canadian balsam fir and Slovak fir, initiated an active interest in the synthesis of these compounds and their various bioanalogues. A large group of geranyl phenyl ethers and their derivatives with high juvenile hormone (JH) activity was first reported by Bowers⁴. Terpenoid ethers derived from geraniol have been found to possess juvenile hormone activity⁵. Aryl terpenoid

ethers in which the terpenoid chain is derived from geraniol, citronellol and ethyl geraniol showed moderate to high activity against *Anopheles quadrimaculatus*⁶ and *Aedes aegypti*⁷. Most of the active compounds contain at least part of a branched carbon chain, characteristic of isoprenoids⁸. We report herein preparation and testing of geranyl-pinyl, geranyl-menthyl ethers and their derivatives.

Results and Discussion

Alkylation⁹ of geranyl bromide¹⁰ A with myrtenol¹¹ (obtained by SeO_2 oxidation of α -pinene in anhydrous ethanol

Scheme 1. Reagents (i) PBr_3 , *n*-hexane, Py, (ii) myrtenol, DMSO, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{CH}$, (iii) menthol, NaH THF, (iv) *m*- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOOH}$, CH_2Cl_2 , 0° , (v) KSCN_3 , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, H_2O , (vi) $\text{N}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, CuSO_4 , 90° , (vii) CHCl_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{N}^+(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{Cl}^-$, 50% NaOH, (viii) CHBr_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{N}^+(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{Cl}^-$, 50% NaOH

to myrtenal followed by subsequent reduction using LiAlH_4 , using methyl sulfinyl carbanion as a base in anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide furnished 1-[(2-pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene **1** (Scheme 1). Alkylation¹² of menthol with geranyl bromide using NaH as a base in anhydrous THF afforded 1-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene **2** in 62.1% yield. Ethers **1** and **2** were converted into their corresponding monoepoxy derivatives **1a** and **2a** by treatment with equimolar amounts of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid¹³. Oxiranes **1a** and **2a** on reaction with KSCN ¹⁴ in ethanol afforded the corresponding thirane derivatives **1b** and **2b**. Reaction of **1** and **2** with ethyl diazoacetate in the presence of copper sulfate furnished 1-[(2-pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-carbathoxymethyl-ene-2(*E*)-octene **1c** and 1-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-carbathoxymethylene-2(*E*)-octene **2c**. Phase transfer catalyzed reaction of **1** and **2** with chloroform/bromoform and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (PTC) in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide gave **1d**, **2d** and **1e**, **2e**. The spectral data of the compounds were consistent with their structures.

Juvenile hormone activity : All the compounds were tested for their juvenile hormone activity against *Culex pipiens quinquefasciatus* Say.¹⁵. The 4th instar larvae of mosquitoes were reared in different doses of the compound for overnight. Their mortality at larval, pupal and adult stages was noted. To find out the activity index, different grades were given to deaths at each stage. The larvae which died at larval stage only, i.e. failed to moult to pupae, was rated as three. The larvae which succeeded in moulting into a pupa but failed to emerge as an adult, was rated as two and the pupa which did emerge into adult but failed to survive, was rated as one. The larvae which successfully reached the adult stage and survived for one day, was rated as zero. The activity index was determined by multiplying the number of larvae at one stage by its numerical value and dividing it by the total number of larvae taken into account. All the experiments were repeated six times to take out the mean mortality at each stage. It was observed that the mortality increased with the increase of dose of the chemical. The activity indices show that the ethers **1**, **2** are quite active on mosquitoes having activity indices 2.28 and 2.79, respectively, at 5 ppm. Their derivatives also showed significant activity. Entomological studies of compounds **1-1e**, **2-2e** along with commercially available JHA-methoprene (M) are reported in Table 1.

Experimental

Progress of all the reactions was monitored by TLC using silica gel impregnated with 13% CaSO_4 . Silica gel (100–

Table 1. Juvenile hormone activity of juvenoids (**1-1e**, **2-2e**) on *Culex pipiens quinquefasciatus* Say.

Compd. no.	Dose in ppm	No. of larvae = 100					Activity index
		0	1	2	3	Activity index	
1	5	0	20	32	48	2.28	
1a	5	0	20	28	52	2.32	
1b	5	0	12	32	56	2.44	
1c	5	0	28	36	36	2.08	
1d	5	0	8	52	40	2.32	
1e	5	0	20	48	32	2.12	
2	5	0	0	21	79	2.79	
2a	5	0	20	20	60	2.4	
2b	5	0	24	48	28	2.04	
2c	5	4	24	16	56	2.24	
2d	5	4	12	48	36	2.2	
2e	5	8	12	24	44	1.92	
M	5	0	0	0	100	3.00	

200 mesh) was used for column chromatography. PMR spectra (CCl_4) were obtained on a Varian 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and IR spectra (neat) on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. Unless otherwise stated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate.

1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene (1**)** : Sodium methyl sulfinyl carbanion was prepared by heating a pre-washed suspension of sodium hydride (1.48 g, 62 mmol; 50% dispersion) in dry DMSO (19.9 ml) at 70° for 1 h. To myrtenol (4.71 g, 31 mmol) dissolved in dry DMSO (20 ml) a trace of triphenylmethane was added. Sodium methyl sulfinyl carbanion was then added to it with stirring and external cooling. To the resulting bright red solution, was added geranyl bromide (7.37 g, 34 mmol) dropwise and stirred for 24 h. It was then decomposed with water (10 ml), extracted with dichloromethane (4 × 50 ml) and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography over silica gel using pet. ether as eluent afforded **1** as pale yellow liquid (3.48 g, 39%, $R_f = 0.659$ in pet. ether : ether (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 83.09; H, 11.01. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}$ requires : C, 83.27; H, 11.18%); ν_{max} 2940, 1680, 1450, 1080, 890 and 810 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.5–5.25 (2H, olefinic proton of pinene ring, C_2 -olefinic proton), 5.15 (1H, C_6 olefinic proton), 4.0–3.8 (4H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O-CH}_2$), 2.3–2.0 (10H, m, 4 × CH_2 , 2 × CH), 1.7 (9H, 3 × $\text{CH}_3\text{-C=C}$), 1.3 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{-C-CH}_3$ of pinene ring), 0.9 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{-C-CH}_3$ of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(*E*),6-octadiene (2**)** : To a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (2.88 g, 120 mmol; 50% suspension) (prewashed

with *n*-hexane) in THF (100 ml), was added solution of menthol (9.36 g, 60 mmol) in THF (20 ml) at 0°. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature followed by refluxing for 6 h at 50°. To the resulting stirred solution was added geranyl bromide (10.85 g, 50 mmol) in THF (10 ml) at room temperature and stirring was continued overnight. After refluxing the contents for 5 h, the reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water (40 ml), extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml), washed successively with 5% NaOH (30 ml) and water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel using pet. ether as eluent afforded pure liquid **2** (9.06 g, 62.1%), $R_f = 0.797$ in pet. ether : ether (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 82.03; H, 12.25. $C_{20}H_{36}O$ requires : C, 82.12; H, 12.40%); v_{max} 2940, 1680, 1100–1050, 920, 790 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.4 (1H, t, J 12 Hz, C_2 -olefinic proton), 5.2 (1H, t like, C_6 -olefinic proton), 4.2–3.8 (2H, m, CH_2-O), 3.2–2.9 (1H, m, O-CH), 2.1 (7H, s, 2 × $CH_2-C=C$, 1 × CH_2-C-O , 1 × CH-C-O), 1.7 (11H, 3 × $CH_3-C=C$, 2 × CH), 1.1–0.8 (13H, m, 3 × CH_3 , 2 × CH_2).

1-[2-Pinen-10-yl]oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxy-2(E)-octene (1a) : To a well stirred ice-cold solution of **1** (2.88 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (100 ml), was added dropwise *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (1.89 g, 11 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (15 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 45 min at 0° and 30 min at room temperature. The resulting solution was decomposed with water, extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 40 ml) washed with 5% sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (25 ml), brine and dried. Solvent was evaporated to give crude residue which was chromatographed over neutral alumina using pet. ether as eluent to give yellow liquid **1a** (2.5 g, 82.5%), $R_f = 0.23$ in pet. ether : ether (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 78.68; H, 10.43. $C_{20}H_{32}O_2$ requires : C, 78.89; H, 10.59%); v_{max} 2940, 1680, 1450, 1100–1060, 880, 810, 760 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.5–5.25 (2H, C_2 -olefinic proton, olefinic proton of pinene ring), 4.0–3.8 (4H, m, CH_2-O-CH_2), 2.6–2.0 (9H, m, 3 × CH_2 , 1 × OCH, 2 × CH), 1.6 (5H, s, 1 × $CH_3-C=C$, 1 × CH_2CO), 1.3 (9H, s, 3 × CH_3), 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3-C-CH_3 of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxy-2(E)-octene (2a) : To a solution of **2** (2.92 g, 10 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) was added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (1.89 g, 11 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) at 0° and the mixture stirred for 1 h at 0° followed by 40 min at 30°. Usual work up followed by purification of the crude product by column chromatography over neutral alumina using pet. ether as eluent afforded **2a** (2.35 g, 76.54%), $R_f = 0.28$ in pet. ether : ether (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 77.72; H, 11.63. $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$ requires : C, 77.86; H, 11.76%); v_{max} 2940, 1680, 1100–1060, 880, 810, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.3 (1H, t, J 18

Hz, C_2 -olefinic proton), 4.1–3.7 (2H, m, CH_2-O), 3.1–2.7 (1H, m, O-CH of cyclohexyl group), 2.5 (1H, t, J 18 Hz, O-CH), 2.2–1.9 (5H, m, 1 × $CH_2C=C$, 1 × CH_2-C-O , 1 × CH-C-O of cyclohexyl group), 1.6 (7H, s, 1 × $CH_3-C=C$, 1 × CH_2CO , 2 × CH), 1.2 (6H, s, 2 × CH_3CO), 1.0–0.75 (13H, m, 3 × CH_3 , 2 × CH_2 of cyclohexyl group).

1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epithio-2(E)-octene (1b) : A solution of KSCN (0.97 g, 10 mmol), oxirane **1a** (3.04 g, 10 mmol) and water (0.099 g, 5.5 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue concentrated, then diluted with ether (20 ml) to precipitate the remaining KOCN, filtered. The solvent was evaporated to give pure liquid **1b** (2.53 g, 79.3%), $R_f = 0.3$ pet. ether : ether (9.0 : 1.0) (Found : C, 74.81; H, 9.3; S, 8.9. $C_{20}H_{32}OS$ requires : C, 74.94; H, 10.06; S, 10.0%); v_{max} 2920, 1670, 1260, 1130, 1080, 810, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.5–5.25 (2H, C_2 -olefinic proton, olefinic proton of pinene ring), 4.0–3.8 (4H, m, CH_2-O-CH_2), 2.55–2.0 (9H, m, 3 × CH_2 , 2 × CH, 1 × SCH), 1.6 (5H, s, 1 × $CH_3-C=C$, 1 × $SCCH_2$), 1.2 (9H, s, 3 × CH_3), 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3-C-CH_3 of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epithio-2(E)-octene (2b) : A mixture of epoxide **2a** (3.08 g, 10 mmol), KSCN (0.97 g, 10 mmol) and water (0.099 g, 5.5 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 24 h at room temperature and worked up according to the procedure reported for **1b** to afford yellow liquid **2b** (2.39 g, 74%), $R_f = 0.37$ in pet. ether : ether (9 : 1) (Found : C, 73.89; H, 11.03; S, 8.88. $C_{20}H_{36}OS$ requires : C, 74.01; H, 11.18; S, 9.87%); v_{max} 2940, 1650, 1100–1050, 920, 880, 790 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.35 (1H, t, J 18 Hz, C_2 -olefinic proton), 4.1–3.8 (2H, m, CH_2-O), 3.1–2.8 (1H, m, O-CH), 2.5–2.0 (6H, m, 1 × $CH_2C=C$, 1 × SCH, 1 × CHCO, 1 × CH_2-C-O). 1.65 (7H, s, 1 × $CH_3-C=C$, CH_2CS , 2 × CH), 1.25 (6H, s, 2 × CH_3CS), 1.0–0.8 (13H, m, 3 × CH_3 , 2 × CH_2 of cyclohexyl group).

1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-carbomethoxy-methylene-2(E)-octene (1c) : To a stirred mixture of **1** (2.88 g, 10 mmol) and freshly prepared anhydrous $CuSO_4$ (0.747 g, 4.7 mmol) at 90° was added dropwise ethyl diazoacetate (1.72 g, 15 mmol) (prepared by diazotization of glycine ethyl ester hydrochloride). It was stirred at this temperature for 2 h, then cooled, diluted with ether (50 ml), filtered and organic layer dried. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over silica gel using pet. ether : ether (9 : 1) to give pure **1c** as pale yellow liquid (1.3 g, 34.8%), $R_f = 0.43$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) (Found : C, 76.82; H, 10.11. $C_{24}H_{38}O_3$ requires : C, 76.96; H, 10.22%); v_{max} 2940, 1740, 1650, 1040, 810, 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 5.5–5.3 (2H, m, C_2 -olefinic proton, olefinic proton of pinene

ring), 4.2–3.7 (6H, m, COOCH₂CH₃, CH₂OCH₂), 2.3–2.0 (9H, m, 3 × CH₂, 1 × CHCOOEt, 2 × CH of pinene ring), 1.6 (4H, s, 1 × CH₃-C=C, 1 × CHCCOOEt), 1.2 (14H, m, 4 × CH₃, 1 × CH₂), 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃-C-CH₃ of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-carbomethoxymethylene-2(E)-octene (2c): Compound **2** (2.92 g, 10 mmol) on treatment with ethyl diazoacetate (1.72 g, 15 mmol) using anhydrous CuSO₄ (0.74 g, 4.7 mmol) as catalyst at 90° and after usual work up, gave crude product which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using pet. ether : ether (9 : 1) to give pure **2c** (1.17 g, 31%); $R_f = 0.54$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) (Found : C, 76.03; H, 11.01. C₂₄H₄₂O₃ requires : C, 76.14; H, 11.18%); ν_{\max} 2940, 1730, 1600, 920, 850 cm⁻¹; δ 5.3 (1H, t, J 18 Hz, C₂-olefinic proton), 4.2–3.7 (4H, m, CH₂O, COOCH₂ CH₃), 3.1–2.7 (1H, m, O-CH), 2.2–1.8 (6H, m, 1 × CH₂-C=C, CHCOOEt, 1 × CH₂CO, 1 × CHCO of cyclohexyl group), 1.6 (6H, CH₃-C=C, 1 × CHCCOOEt, 2 × CH of cyclohexyl group), 1.2–1.0 (11H, s, 3 × CH₃, 1 × CH₂), 0.9 (13H, m, 3 × CH₃, 2 × CH₂ of cyclohexyl group).

1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bisdichloromethylene octane (1d): A mixture of **1** (1.44 g, 5 mmol) in chloroform (15 ml) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.273 g, 1.2 mmol) (prepared from equimolar amounts of triethylamine and benzyl chloride in acetone) was stirred until the salt dissolved. Then 50% NaOH solution (7 ml) was added to it and stirring continued for further 3 days. The resulting solution was diluted with water (50 ml), extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Solvent was evaporated to afford TLC-pure thick liquid **1d** (1.88 g, 83.3%), $R_f = 0.62$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 58.08; H, 6.89. C₂₂H₃₂OCl₄ requires : C, 58.16; H, 7.1%); ν_{\max} 2940, 1680, 1270, 1090, 830 cm⁻¹; δ 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic proton of pinene ring), 3.9–3.5 (4H, m, CH₂-O-CH₂), 2.4–2.1 (6H, 2 × CH₂, 2 × CH), 1.8–1.2 (18H, 4 × CH₃, 2 × CHCl₂, 2 × CH₂), 0.9 (3H, s, CH₃-C-CH₃ of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bisdichloromethylene octane (2d): A mixture of **2** (1.46 g, 5 mmol) in chloroform (30 ml), NaOH (50%) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.273 g, 1.2 mmol) was stirred for 3 days and after usual work up as described for **1d** afforded **2d** (1.71 g, 75%), $R_f = 0.76$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 57.50; H, 7.74. C₂₂H₃₆OCl₄ requires : C, 57.65; H, 7.91%); ν_{\max} 2940, 1100–1060, 920, 840, 790 cm⁻¹; δ 4.1–3.5 (2H, m, CH₂O), 3.2–2.9 (1H, m, OCH), 2.4–1.2 (20H, m, 3 × CH₃, 5 × CH, 3 × CH₂), 1.0–0.8 (13H, d, J 9 Hz, 3 × CH₃, 2 × CH₂ of cyclohexyl group).

1-[(2-Pinen-10-yl)oxy]-3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bisdibromomethylene octane (1e): A solution of **1** (1.44 g, 5 mmol), bromoform (16 ml) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.273 g, 1.2 mmol) was stirred until the salt dissolved. Then aq. NaOH (50%; 10 ml) was added and stirring continued for 48 h. Water was poured into the reaction mixture, extracted with bromoform and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Removal of solvent afforded TLC-pure **1e** (2.59 g, 82%), $R_f = 0.6$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 41.63; H, 5.02. C₂₂H₃₂OBr₄ requires : C, 41.80; H, 5.10%); ν_{\max} 2940, 1250, 1090, 750, 690, 650 cm⁻¹; δ 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic proton of pinene ring), 3.85–3.5 (4H, m, CH₂OCH₂), 2.4–2.0 (6H, m, 2 × CH₂, 2 × CH of pinene ring), 1.8–1.2 (18H, m, 4 × CH₃, 2 × CHCBr₂, 2 × CH₂), 0.85 (3H, s, CH₃-C-CH₃ of pinene ring).

1-(2'-Isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyloxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bisdibromomethylene octane (2e): A mixture of **2** (1.46 g, 5 mmol), bromoform (30 ml) and NaOH (50%) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.273 g, 1.2 mmol) was stirred for 50 h, then worked up according to the procedure described for **1e**. Evaporation of the solvent afforded pure **2e** (2.48 g, 78.2%), $R_f = 0.72$ in pet. ether : ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5) (Found : C, 41.38; H, 5.52. C₂₂H₃₆OBr₄ requires : C, 41.53; H, 5.70%); ν_{\max} 2920, 1100, 790, 700, 660 cm⁻¹; δ 4.1–3.5 (2H, m, CH₂O), 3.2–2.9 (1H, m, CHO), 2.3–1.2 (20H, m, 3 × CH₃, 5 × CH, 3 × CH₂), 0.9 (13H, d, J 9 Hz, 3 × CH₃, 2 × CH₂ of cyclohexyl group).

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